

high with a 3:1 ratio. Golden snail meat meal can safely replace fish or meat meal in food animal diets.

Shell meal was Ca-rich, with 35.05% Ca. It could potentially replace oyster shell meal.

Table 2 shows average production performance of growing/finishing pigs fed GSM-supplemented diets. The response criteria—average daily gain, average daily feed consumption, and average feed conversion efficiency—

showed insignificant differences across treatments.

The results indicate GSM could be used as a feed supplement for growing/finishing pigs. □

Loss of rice grain yield and seedling vigor due to sheath rot (ShR) and mealy bug interaction

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We observed a severe ShR *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams and Hawksw. outbreak in Sep-Oct 1990 in IR20 ricefields infected with mealy bug *Brevinnia rehi* Lindinger.

The flag leaf of individual tillers was assessed and tagged with waterproof color tape according to ShR severity at grain maturity stage. The *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) was

used. About 100 samples, replicated five times, represented each severity class.

Mealy bugs inside ShR-infected sheaths were counted for each class. Panicles within seventy classes were bulked, dried separately. Thousand-grain weight and percent of healthy, discolored, and chaffy grains were recorded.

We evaluated seedling vigor after storage for 1 mo at room temperature with a standard test. Fifty seeds were incubated between double-layer blotter paper in 9-cm plates for 2 wk at 25°C with four replications per sample. We recorded the number of germinated seeds, and shoot and root lengths after 2 wk.

ShR severity was positively correlated ($r = 0.99^{**}$) with mealy bug population (see figure). Their interaction greatly reduced 1,000-grain weight, grain yield (9-77%), and healthy grains percentage; it increased chaffy and discolored grains.

Correlation of sheath rot severity and mealy bug population Sep-Oct 1990 at ACRI.

Seed germination and root length were significantly reduced, but shoot length was not. □

Water management

Water use by irrigated summer rice

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We measured use of water by summer rice through evapotranspiration and deep percolation. Soils were medium black, clay loam texture, pH 6.9, 0.82% organic C, infiltration rate 1.0-1.5 cm/h.

The technique used two 200-liter capacity leakproof drums, 60 cm in diameter and 90 cm high. One drum had

an open bottom; the second, a closed bottom. The drums were installed in oversized pits 60 cm deep and 65 cm in diameter in the ricefield, leaving about 30 cm of the drum height aboveground. The soil was backfilled layerwise and compacted to approximately the same bulk density as that of the surrounding soil.

Mean evapotranspiration use and deep percolation loss at different growth phases of summer rice.^a Maharashtra, India, 1987-89.

	Water use (mm)									
	Open-bottom drum					Closed-bottom drum				
	Transplanting to maximum tillering	Maximum tillering to flowering	Flowering to milk stage	Milk to maturity	Total (90 d)	Transplanting to maximum tillering	Maximum tillering to flowering	Flowering to milk stage	Milk to maturity	Total (90 d)
Total evapotranspiration + deep percolation	528.3	678.9	342.0	450.4	1999.6	280.8	372.9	203.9	271.0	1128.5
Average/d	21.1	22.6	22.8	22.5	-	11.2	12.4	13.6	13.6	-
Through evapotranspiration	-	-	-	-	-	280.8	372.9	203.9	271.0	1128.5
Through deep percolation	247.5	306.0	138.2	179.4	871.1	-	-	-	-	-
Deep percolation/d	9.9	10.2	9.2	8.9	-	-	-	-	-	-
Percolation (%)	46.9	45.1	40.4	39.8	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aAv for 3 yr.